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Research Article

**FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH POOR BLOOD PRESSURE
CONTROL AMONG HYPERTENSIVE PATIENTS IN RURAL
AREAS OF PAKISTAN**¹Dr Virdah Farooq, ²Dr Humaira Qasim, ³Dr Jaza Abbas¹Quaid e Azam Medical College²Quaid e Azam Medical College³Madina Teaching Hospital Faisalabad**Article Received:** July 2020**Accepted:** August 2020**Published:** September 2020**Abstract:**

We have seen that people suffering from a cardiac issue as hypertension which create a major problem in people and cause serious heart diseases. We make this report to check what are the main problems which cause poor blood control which may cause serious issues. We take survey where we examine about 391 respondents who was in the age of about 28-30 above years old. By asking questions we collect data and then summarize it. After collecting of data we use different methods to get accurate result, which will help us to complete our report. We check out the results and seen the rate of blood control in those people who was hypertensive and level of blood present last time when they checked. By making all these results we make this study report and it is concluded that we should spend most our time on it and do proper research to treat poor control of blood pressure and hypertension which cause serious issues as heart attacks, cardiac vessels block and traumas which causes death.

Key Words: Cardiac diseases, poor control of blood pressure, respondents, serious traumas.

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INTRODUCTION:

Hypertension is a worldwide issue which spread in whole world and causing serious issues for heart [1]. It effects heart badly and cause different diseases if there is a poor control of blood pressure in humans who are hypertensive. Risk of hypertension is increasing day by day also in young one [2]. In 2014 when this study make it estimated that this risk of hypertension will be increased up to 62% after 10% years if it will not be controlled. It affects more to those people whose body weight is increased or level of cholesterol in the body will be increased [3]. This type of people will from this disease more than others. This causes different problems to different body organs. As it effects heart and cause heart failure through which death can occur and also cause many other problems in human body [4]. People did not know about these diseases, because of unawareness they cannot take care of their selves according to requirements and they continue eating those food which they do not have to use during hypertension or blood pressure problems. People who live in rural areas are not well educated [5]. They don't know about the thing which they have to eat and which they don't have to eat. They don't have much knowledge medicines; most of them drink alcohol [6]. This type of behavior makes them habitual of their bodies in this result this poor control of blood pressure happens. It also occurs in those people too who are depressed which their routine life and due to this depression they started using alcohol. So risk of hypertension increased gradually [7]. We see patients who were suffering from hypertension and poor control of blood pressure was attending sessions and treatments in hospitals. Some of them were new who started treatment soon [8]. Some of them were 50% cured with thus disease. Ratio of hypertensive patients is also increased in other

Table: 1

Socio-demographic characteristics	Frequency	%	Mean± SD	95%CI
Gender				
Male	131	33.6		
Female	259	66.4		
Age(years old)			63.52±12.92	62.27-64.84
30 to less than 40	14	3.6		
40 to less than 50	42	10.8		
50 to less than 59	96	24.6		
60 to less than 69	92	23.6		
70 and above	146	37.4		
Marital status				
Single	5	1.3		
Married	310	79.5		
Divorced/Widowed	75	19.2		
Level of education				
Illiterate	242	62.0		

countries as compared to Pakistan because of unawareness of this disease [9].So it is must to make different strategies and aware to those people who are living in rural areas and having less knowledge about this disease which causes deaths of hypertensive patients [10].

METHODOLOGY:

We make study in which we take different number of respondents. People who were hypertensive were with the age of about 28-30 years. We visit to different respondents and about 391 respondents help us to complete this study by filling up the survey form and telling us about the real situation which they have face ad are still facing. We use a simple method to collect the data and make our study report in form of survey. They have given proper time in which they can properly think and guide us about their experiences and answer our questions more accurately. With situational we also examine their total weight of body, their physical activities, and their level of blood pressure in their body at that time. We also check out the stressed level. By asking question we make sure that who is mentally stressed and at which stage. After completing the question answer session, we collect all papers from respondents and start working on it. We also take views of those doctors who help us in this task who examine those hypertensive patients. By taking permissions from higher committees. After completing all documentations, we make results. After completion of data, rechecking of this data occur. After this checking and rechecking process data analyze and report get ready.

RESULTS:

Respondents we take as about 391.They belong to different age groups but most of them were old. Some of them was married and some were unmarried, rate of illiteracy was about 60%.Details are shown in the following table.

Primary school	138	35.4		
Secondary school	8	2.0		
High school	1	0.3		
Diploma/University	1	0.3		
Job				
Business	21	5.4		
Farmer	84	21.5		
Retired	18	4.6		
Jobless	47	12.1		

10 Rials=1 Tomans=0.001 USD

Rate of increasing level of hypertension is different in men and women. In women ratio they get high level of hypertension when they moved up to 50 years but in men it started increasing when their ages increase 71 years. Table two shows the level of blood pressure control in both men and women.

Table: 2

Age Group (years)	Good BP control (n=177)			Poor BP control (n=213)		
	Male n= (%)	Female n= (%)	Total n= (%)	Male n= (%)	Female n= (%)	Total n= (%)
30-39	0 (0.0)	5 (4.2)	5 (4.2)	1 (1.4)	8 (5.7)	9 (4.2)
40-49	1 (1.7)	18 (15.3)	19 (10.7)	1 (1.4)	22 (15.6)	23 (10.7)
50-59	14 (23.7)	29 (24.6)	43 (24.3)	5 (6.9)	48 (34.0)	53 (24.8)
60-69	15 (25.4)	22 (18.6)	37 (20.9)	16 (22.2)	39 (27.7)	55 (25.8)
>70	29 (49.2)	44 (37.3)	73 (41.2)	49 (68.1)	24 (17.0)	73 (34.2)
Total	59 (100.0)	118 (100.0)	117 (100.0)	72 (100.0)	141 (100.0)	213 (100.0)

The percentages of blood pressure control in those who do smoking with contrast to those did not do smoking in their lives. So we see results that people who do smoking in their live have increasing rate of hypertension as compared to others.

Table: 3

Factors	B	S.E	P	OR	95% CI
Level of physical activity					
High				1.00	
Moderate	0.92	0.47	0.050	2.51	1.00-6.31
Low	4.88	0.68	<0.001*	131.30	34.52-40099.33
BMI category					
Underweight/normal weight				1.00	
Over weight	1.23	0.41	0.003*	3.42	1.52-7.71
Obese	1.78	0.56	0.002*	5.91	1.97-17.78
BP control status during the last visit					

Good				1.00	
Poor	2.86	0.40	<0.001*	17.42	8.02-37.80
Number of anti-hypertensive used					
2drugs and more				1.00	
I drug	2.43	0.52	<0.001*	11.32	4.08-31.42
Compliance to medication					
Yes				1.00	
No	1.29	0.38	<0.001*	3.62	1.74-7.55
Interval between Dr's visit					
<3months				1.00	
>3months	1.76	0.46	<0.001*	5.82	2.36-14.35

DISCUSSION:

We make this report and get an important point about less control of blood pressure is due to lack of physical activities [11]. If person will not be physically fit, or if he will spend most of his time on bed and not type of physical activity will be included in his routine then it will affect its level of blood present and change it into poor control [12]. So due to less physical fitness their body weight increased gradually, so to treat that issue we have to make them habitual to do exercise daily and help them to reduce their weight [13]. In this way they can overcome this disease and we saved a lot of lives. Regular checkup also helps a lot to control hypertension [14]. Because with this study we assume that people who go to hospital for their regular checkup. Doctors do their treatment and check their Bp in this way their blood pressure will be control but people who do not visit doctors will have increasing affects of poor control of blood pressure and hypertension in their bodies [15]. People who are taking drugs or medicines in fewer amounts will have less level of hypertension as compare to those who are taking multiple drugs [16]. So as we know that hypertension cause serious issues as failure of hearts, and traumas and many other diseases related to heart which cause serious damage which may cause death. So to overcome this issue we have to spread awareness about this disease especially in rural areas [17].

CONCLUSION:

After this survey we have concluded that treatment rate is not able to satisfy. People who have poor control of blood pressure with hypertension. There are several; causes which make these type of issues as usage of drugs in daily life, less taking healthy food, lack of physical activities and somehow mental stress is also included. To get rid of all these issue we have to spread awareness to avoid disasters happen due to this disease and to decrease death rate.

REFERENCES:

1. Woodham, N. S., Taneepanichskul, S., Somrongthong, R., Kitsanapun, A., & Sompakdee, B. (2020). Effectiveness of a

Multidisciplinary Approach Intervention to Improve Blood Pressure Control Among Elderly Hypertensive Patients in Rural Thailand: A Quasi-Experimental Study. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Healthcare*, 13, 571.

2. Mathur, D., Deora, S., Kaushik, A., Bhardwaj, P., & Singh, K. (2020). Awareness, medication adherence, and diet pattern among hypertensive patients attending teaching institution in western Rajasthan, India. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 9(5), 2342.
3. Gebre, B. B., Deribe, B., & Abeto, M. (2020). Magnitude and Associated Factors of Depression Among Hypertensive Patients Attending Treatment Follow Up in Chronic OPD at Hawassa University Comprehensive Specialized Hospital, Hawassa, Southern Ethiopia. *Integrated Blood Pressure Control*, 13, 31.
4. Fekadu, G., Adamu, A., Gebre, M., Gamachu, B., Bekele, F., Abadiga, M., ... & Oluma, A. (2020). Magnitude and Determinants of Uncontrolled Blood Pressure Among Adult Hypertensive Patients on Follow-Up at Nekemte Referral Hospital, Western Ethiopia. *Integrated Blood Pressure Control*, 13, 49.
5. Gupta, R. D., Haider, S. S., Sutradhar, I., Hasan, M., Joshi, H., Haider, M. R., & Sarker, M. (2020). Gender differences in hypertension awareness, antihypertensive use and blood pressure control in Nepalese adults: findings from a nationwide cross-sectional survey. *Journal of Biosocial Science*, 52(3), 412-438.
6. Gupta, S., Kumar, R., Kalavani, M., Nongkynrih, B., Kant, S., & Gupta, S. K. (2020). Prevalence, awareness, treatment, and control of diabetes and hypertension among elderly persons in a rural area of Ballabgarh, Haryana. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 9(2), 777.
7. Xin, B., Li, Y., & Wang, Y. (2020). Associated factors with awareness, treatment and control of hypertension among 3,579 hypertensive

- adults in China: data from the China Health and Nutrition Survey.
8. Agongo, G., Nonterah, E. A., Amenga-Etego, L., Debuur, C., Kaburise, M. B., Ali, S. A., ... & Oduro, A. R. (2020). Blood Pressure Indices and Associated Risk Factors in a Rural West African Adult Population: Insights from an AWI-Gen Substudy in Ghana. *International Journal of Hypertension*, 2020.
 9. Kang, G. C. Y., Koh, E. Y. L., & Tan, N. C. (2020). Prevalence and factors associated with adherence to anti-hypertensives among adults with hypertension in a developed Asian community: A cross-sectional study. *Proceedings of Singapore Healthcare*, 2010105820933305.
 10. Souza, N. P. D., Cesse, E. Â. P., Souza, W. V. D., Fontbonne, A., Barreto, M. N. S. D. C., Goff, M. L., ... & Lira, P. I. C. D. (2020). Temporal variation in prevalence, awareness and control of hypertension in urban and rural areas in Northeast Brazil between 2006 and 2016. *Cadernos de Saúde Pública*, 36(4).
 11. Lekamwasam, S., Wijebandara, S., & Lekamwasam, V. (2020). Health Literacy and Control of Glycaemia in Diabetes and Blood Pressure in Hypertension; A Study Based on Validated Sinhala Version of HLS-EU-Q16. *Asian Journal of Medicine and Health*, 12-18.
 12. Beune, E., Nieuwkerk, P., Stronks, K., Meeks, K., Schulze, M. B., Mockenhaupt, F. P., ... & Addo, J. (2019). Medication non-adherence and blood pressure control among hypertensive migrant and non-migrant populations of sub-Saharan African origin: the RODAM study. *Journal of human hypertension*, 33(2), 131-148.
 13. Kimani, S., Mirie, W., Chege, M., Okube, O. T., & Muniu, S. (2019). Association of lifestyle modification and pharmacological adherence on blood pressure control among patients with hypertension at Kenyatta National Hospital, Kenya: a cross-sectional study. *BMJ open*, 9(1), e023995.
 14. Macquart de Terline, D., Kane, A., Kramoh, K. E., Ali Toure, I., Mipinda, J. B., Diop, I. B., ... & Ikama, M. S. (2019). Factors associated with poor adherence to medication among hypertensive patients in twelve low and middle income Sub-Saharan countries. *PloS one*, 14(7), e0219266.
 15. Nassr, O. A., & Forsyth, P. (2019). Evaluation of blood pressure control and associated factors among patients with hypertension in Iraq: a prospective cross-sectional study. *Journal of pharmacy & bioallied sciences*, 11(3), 232.
 16. Mwangi, E. M., Nyamu, D. G., Njogu, P. M., & Karimi, P. N. (2019). Antihypertensive therapy and adequacy of blood pressure control among adult hypertensive diabetic patients with chronic kidney disease in a tertiary referral hospital. *Hospital Practice*, 47(3), 136-142.
 17. Song, H., Zhang, D., Chen, Z., Wang, R., Tang, S., Bishwajit, G., ... & Su, Y. (2019). Utilisation of national community-based blood pressure monitoring service among adult Chinese and its association with hypertension treatment and blood pressure control—a mediation analysis. *BMC geriatrics*, 19(1), 1-12.